

**SOCIAL EXCLUSION AND MARGINALIZATION OF MUSLIMS
IN HIGHER EDUCATION: AN APPRAISAL OF ALL INDIA
SURVEY ON HIGHER EDUCATION 2020-21**

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Abstract

Access to Education plays a pivotal role in empowering marginalized and excluded communities, as it serves as a vital component in the pursuit of a fair and inclusive society. This research paper examines the social exclusion and marginalization of Muslims in higher Education in contemporary India, focusing on the All India Survey on Higher Education 2020-21 findings. Despite efforts towards inclusive policies, Muslims continue to lag behind their counterparts in terms of educational attainment. This study aims to explore the factors contributing to this disparity, including socio-economic factors, discrimination, and limited representation. Through a comprehensive analysis of the survey data and relevant literature, the paper highlights the urgency of addressing these challenges and proposes policy interventions to promote inclusivity in higher Education. The findings may contribute to the perspectives on the ongoing dialogue on social justice and equitable access to Education in India.

Keywords: *Muslims, Social Exclusion, Higher Education, AISHE 2020-21*

India is a multilingual, multireligious, and multicultural country. Its exciting diversity, civilizational history, and emergence as a growing economic and military power have attracted the attention of scholars and researchers across the globe. India's exciting diversity has led to describe it as the 'confederation of minorities'. India's Constitution recognizes this diversity and aims to promote the interest of all through 'authoritative allocation of values' (Easton, David, 2017); on the one hand, it provides equality and justice to all without any discrimination on the grounds of religion, castes, sex, place of birth, etc., on the other hand, it also has provisions for uplifting the historically disadvantaged and socially

excluded groups through special measures. Muslims constitute 14% of the country's population and are the most significant religious minority in India. However, they are among the most backward segments of the country. {See The Gopal Singh Committee Report 1983, The Sachar Committee Report 2006}. Since independence, they have faced many challenges relating to their security, Education, employment, progress, etc. The relative backwardness of the Muslim community calls for the need to address the specific concerns of the Muslim community to ensure inclusive progress and equal opportunities for all.

It is well established that enhancements in children's and youth's functional and analytical capacities through Education create opportunities that empower individuals and groups, granting them entitlements and benefits. Education serves as a powerful means to combat social exclusion and marginalization within society. Providing individuals with access to quality education can break the cycle of exclusion and empower marginalized communities to overcome barriers and achieve social mobility. Education equips individuals with the tools to challenge societal inequalities and discrimination, enabling them to actively participate in economic, social, and political spheres. Through Education, we can foster inclusivity, bridge the gap between different segments of society, and create a more equitable and cohesive community.

However, the educational scenario in India remains unequal, with the Muslim minority facing multiple barriers that hinder their educational progress and perpetuate social disparities. Various government reports and commissions established the educational exclusion and marginalization of Muslims. The All India Report on Higher Education 2020-21 shows a concerning decline in the enrolment of Muslim students in both general and higher Education. Contributing factors like the discontinuation of MANF affect Muslim research scholars. Similarly, the controversial issue of banning hijab (currently under review by the Supreme Court) has impacted the dropout rate of Muslim girls from educational institutes. The state provided the option for Muslim female students to choose Education or hijab. This attitude of the government is against the spirit of the Constitution and the 'Muslim identity.'

This paper aims to analysis the social exclusion of Muslims in Higher Education, based on the All India Survey on Higher Education 2020-21 and other government-sponsored reports. This study seeks to understand

the underlying factors contributing to this disparity by examining enrolment trends, dropout rates, and representation. The repeal of the Maulana Azad Fellowship (MANF) is expected to have a significant impact on Muslim students. This study also assesses the impact of the repeal of the MANF on the educational opportunities and support for Muslim students. Besides, it seeks to understand the challenges faced by Muslim women who wear the hijab and analyze the consequences on their educational opportunities. Also research paper aims to provide insights for effective policy interventions and initiatives promoting inclusivity in Higher Education through rigorous analysis and literature review.

Discussion

(Marginalization and Social Exclusion of Muslims in Higher Education: An Evidence)

Social exclusion and marginalization are pervasive phenomena that impact societies globally, encompassing the systematic disadvantage and exclusion of certain groups from various social, economic, and political opportunities. Exclusion can occur at the individual, community, and societal levels, and in the context of communities, it often manifests through the stigmatization of identity, such as caste, ethnicity, or religion. Kabeer emphasized the importance of a social exclusion perspective beyond poverty to understand how specific groups are systematically "locked out" or left behind in various dimensions due to their identity (Kabeer 2006). Amartya Sen stated that there is capability deprivation in which 'unfavorable inclusion' and unfavorable exclusion in which 'unfavorable exclusion, where some people are being kept out even though they are capable; the other hand, 'unfavorable inclusion,' where some people are being included-may even be forced to be included (Sen, Amartya,2000). In the Indian context, religious minorities, particularly Muslims, often confront social, economic, and political disadvantages due to religious discrimination and stereotyping (Kundu & Sinha, 2020). The educational marginalization and social exclusion of Muslims in Higher Education is a significant concern in India. Muslims, as a religious minority group, face multiple challenges in accessing and progressing through higher Education, which impacts their socio-economic development and overall well-being (Kumar, 2015).

Marginalization of Muslims in all walks of life is not a new phenomenon in India. Gopal Singh Committee Report 1983 empirically established the fact of marginalization of Muslims in education spaces. It revealed that Muslim student representation in higher Education is deficient compared to their population (Singh Gopal, 1983). The leading cause of the backwardness of Muslims in Education was due as much to poverty (Singh, Gopal.1983).

The backwardness of Muslims in Education can be attributed to factors such as poverty, lack of interest in secular Education, limited access to technical institutions, and the underrepresentation of women in Education. Muslims face economic challenges due to educational shortcomings, leading to a substantial population engaged in traditional crafts and unable to avail of better opportunities for progress (Singh, Gopal, 1983). On this similar condition, Amartya Sen says that in his capability deprivation approach, poverty is not solely about income but the freedoms and opportunities individuals have to lead lives they value. Regarding the educational backwardness of Muslims, multiple factors intersect to limit their capabilities. Economic constraints limit access to quality education, and Gender disparities restrict the educational opportunities for women, impeding their agency and potential contributions to society. This deprivation hampers their capability to make choices, pursue diverse opportunities, and engage meaningfully in socio-economic spheres. Breaking this cycle requires addressing access, quality, relevance, government affirmative actions, and cultural sensitivities in education institutions (Sen, 2000).

Table- 1

Communities	Professional Courses			
	B.Sc (ENGG.) / B.E		MBBS	
	%	Appeared Students B.SC (ENGG.) B.E./ MBBS	%	Population %
Muslim	3.41%		3.44%	12.44%
Christians	7.23%		6.14%	5.40%
Sikhs	1.70%		7.42%	1.90%

Source- Gopal Singh Report 1983. * Please see the NOTE for detailed information.

It is crucial to notice that the educational backwardness of Muslims increases year by year, as evident from the report of the Sachar committee, which finds out that the education gap between Muslims and the general population has widened over time, especially in higher Education. In contrast, Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes have made progress, possibly due to targeted programs and job reservation policies that have improved access to education and economic opportunities (Sachar committee, 2006). Sachar Committee stated that "Muslims will be far behind even the S.C.s/S.T.s if the trend is not reversed (Sachar Committee, 2006).

According to the Sachar Committee Report, In IITs, only 894 out of 27,161 enrolled students were Muslims, representing approximately 4% of post-graduate courses and merely 1.7% of undergraduate courses. The representation of Muslims in Ph.D. courses was better compared to other courses. Similarly, in premier colleges in India, the enrolment of Muslims is significantly low, with only one out of twenty-five students in undergraduate courses and one out of fifty students in post-graduate courses being Muslim. The representation of Muslims in top Medical colleges was marginally better, accounting for around 4% of students across courses such as MBBS, Dental, and Nursing(Sachar Committee, 2006).

It is interesting to note that the Higher Graduation Attainment Rate (GAR) varies among different age groups. Muslims have a higher GAR than most SRCs among individuals aged 51 years and above. However, in the 20-30 years age group, the GAR for Muslims is surpassed by H-OBC, while the GAR for SC/ST is increasing at a faster pace.

This pattern did not change when the Kundu Committee submitted its report, which stated that the Muslim community still lags behind in terms of graduate and technical Education (Kundu Report, 2012).

Through various reports, it is evident that Muslims are highly marginalized in Education. Therefore, the Sachar Committee Report and the Ranganath Mishra Commission Report recommended that the most rational and justifiable policy for the government would be to implement positive discrimination measures in favour of Muslims. Consequently, some Southern states have taken steps in this direction and witnessed positive outcomes in addressing the educational and socio-economic disparities Muslims face (Jaffrelot & Kalaiyaran, 2023). However, since

Muslims are spread over across the country, it is crucial to have a national level affirmative action programme for Muslims. Because Muslims face varying levels of social exclusion in Education across different regions and economic settings in India. Therefore, categorizing Muslims as a single group becomes even more irrelevant and questionable when developing policies (Hasan, 2011).

The budget for the Minority Affairs Ministry has been reduced by over 38% to Rs 30,0976 million for 2023-24, compared to 50,205 million in the previous fiscal year. This reduction raises concerns about the possible exclusion and discrimination faced by minority communities in India despite an overall increase in the education budget (Dirghangi, A & Anas, O, 2023). Furthermore, the Ministry of Minority Affairs has discontinued the Maulana Azad Fellowship, a dedicated initiative to support minority students pursuing higher education, effective from the academic year-2022-23. This decision further restricts access to educational opportunities for minority students, including Muslims, and hampers their ability to pursue higher studies (The Wire Staff, 2022). Budget cuts by the Minority Affairs Ministry have raised concerns about the marginalization and discrimination of minority communities.

The discontinuation of the MANF program had a devastating impact on young scholars, particularly women, who relied on the program to pursue research and alleviate the financial burden of higher education. For many female scholars, discontinuing this program can effectively halt their educational pursuits.

The ban on hijab in government-run and minority-aided educational institutions undermines the limited progress made in facilitating educational opportunities for Muslims. The lower educational opportunities for Muslims. The lower educational achievements within the Muslim community are primarily attributed to socio- economic factors rather than regressive practices or backwardness (T.K.2022). There is research conducted in five districts of Karnataka, total 1,010 hijab wearing girls dropped out of P.U. colleges "because of hijab ban and other reasons as well" (The Indian Express,2023). Therefore, Muslim women students not only encounter barriers to their right to education but also endure a climate of hate and misinformation, which is protected under articles 15, 19(1) (a), 21 of the Constitution.

Therefore, Amartya Sen, in his notable work "Development as Freedom", written under the section "Women's Agency and Social Change," stated that transforming women's 'ill-being' through financial independence highlights the important link between women's education, gainful employment, and their empowerment (Sen Amartya, 2000).

The discontinuation of the MANF has left Muslim women, who are already minorities within minorities, without support and has stifled their aspirations. This abrupt change has left many girls from minority communities stranded, unable to fulfill their ambitions that surpass the expectations of their parents and society (Khatoun, Abida,2023).

However, the assertion that the MANAF overlaps with other open-to-programms further undermines the notion of equal opportunities and inclusivity. This stark contrast exposes the gap between the ideals of a just society and the reality of unequal access and opportunities.

All India Survey on Higher Education: An Appraisal

The All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) was launched in 2011 with the aim of gathering comprehensive data on higher Education in India. Prior to its inception, existing data sources on higher education failed to provide a holistic view of the sector. Therefore, the AISHE was introduced to fill this crucial information gap and provide a more accurate and complete picture of higher education in the country. The survey collected data for the year 2010-11 and has since been instrumental in informing policy decisions and facilitating a deeper understanding of the state of higher Education in India (AISHE, 2023).

The All India Survey on Higher Education 2020-21 reveals the contrasting trend in enrolment patterns. The data shows a positive increase in enrolment rates for Dalits, Adivasis, and OBCs, with growth rates of 4.2%, 11.9%, and 4% respectively compared to the 2019-2020 year. In contrast, the enrolment of Muslim students experienced a significant decline of 8%, resulting in a decrease of 1,79,147 students. This absolute decline in enrolment is unprecedented and has not been observed in recent years for any other demographic group. Additionally, the upper castes, whose enrolment had been decreasing due to the implementation of Mandal II, experienced the highest growth rate of 13.6% in this period.

Year-wise enrolment of Muslims and other minorities. Here is the decline in enrolment of Muslims compared to 2019-2020 survey.

Source – AISHE 2020-21, FIG.55.

According to the Sachar Committee Report, as mentioned in the discussion part, the educational condition of Muslims was found to be on par with, or even worse than, the most marginalized communities in the country. Since then, their marginalization has further intensified. Initially, Muslims had a slightly better educational standing than Dalits, but by 2017,18, Dalits had surpassed them. In 2020-21, it was the turn of Adivasis to surpass Muslims in terms of educational attainment (AISHE, 2023 p.45,46).

The analysis of PLFS data, specifically focusing on the age cohort of 18-23, reinforces this pattern, indicating that Muslims fare even worse than Dalits and Adivasis. According to the available data, only around 19% of Muslims are currently enrolled in higher education institutions. In comparison, Adivasis have a higher enrolment rate at 21%, Dalits at 26%, Hindu OBCs at 34% and Hindu upper castes at 45% (Jaffrelot & Kalaiyaran, 2023).

When examining major states in the year 2020-21, no state except Tamil Nadu, Telangana, and Delhi showed better educational outcome for Muslims compared to Dalits. Additionally, Adivasis outperforms Muslims in several states, including Rajasthan, Assam, Gujrat, Maharashtra, and Jharkhand. These findings shed light on the disparities in educational

access and opportunities that persist for Muslims in various regions across India

Among the states contributing to the decline in Muslim student enrolment, Uttar Pradesh (UP) accounts for 36% of the total decrease, followed by Jammu and Kashmir with 26%, Maharashtra with 8.5%, Tamil Nadu with 8.1%, Gujrat with 6.1%, Bihar with 5.7%, and Karnataka with 3.7%. Notably, Tamil Nadu is the only state where Muslims alone experienced an absolute decline in enrolment. It is observed that states with a larger Muslim population share a higher proportion of the enrolment decline, but even smaller states exhibit similar trends. For Instance, between 2019-20 and 2020-21, Delhi witnessed a decrease of approximately 20% in its Muslim student population, while Jammu and Kashmir saw a decline of about 36%.

States Wise Decrease

Source – AISHE, FIG.1.2.

The state of Uttar Pradesh (UP), the most populous state in India, holds significant weight when determining the national average. However, despite Muslims constituting about 20% of the state's population, their representation in higher education enrolment is disproportionately low at just 4.5%. This discrepancy raises concerns about the limited access and opportunities available to Muslim students in UP. Moreover, UP alone

witnessed a substantial dropout of 58,365 Muslim students from the previous academic year (2019-20), indicating a decline of 16%. This decline in enrolment and dropout rate further accentuates the deepening educational deprivation faced by Muslims in the state.

On the other hand, the state of Kerala offers a contrasting narrative of progress and upward mobility for its Muslim population. In addition to experiencing positive enrollment growth, Kerala stands out with the highest percentage of Muslim youth (43%) currently attending higher education. This achievement can be attributed to Kerala's long-standing policy of positive discrimination, which has actively worked to create a more equitable educational landscape. The century-old practice of providing affirmative action and preferential treatment to Muslims has played a significant role in empowering the community and fostering educational capital within the state. As a result, Kerala serves as an example of how targeted interventions and inclusive policies can lead to improved academic outcomes for marginalized communities. In Kerala, Muslims in the state benefit from a 10% reservation in govt. jobs and a 12% reservation in educational institutions. (Jaffrelot & Kalaiyarasan,2023). For Instance, in J&K, Muslims account for 67% of the population but have a low literacy rate of 47%. In contrast, in Kerala, where Muslims make up approximately 25% of the population, the literacy rate among Muslims is high 89% (R.M.Report, 2007).

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If we see the representation in terms of gender distribution, it is the number of female teachers per 100 male teachers at the All India level, in which Muslim women's representation is deficient.

Source – AISHE 2020-21, Fig, 30

While, at the national level, the distribution of teachers is as follows: 56.2% belong to the General category, 32.2% are classified as OBC, 9.1% are S.C., and 2.5% are S.T. Among the teacher population, approximately 5.6% represent the Muslim minority group, while 8.8% come from other minority groups (AISHE, 2023, p.30).

Percentage share of teachers, social group wise, for top ten states with highest no of teachers

Source: AISHE 2020-21, fig.29

The All India Level survey on Non- Teaching staff in institutions provides data only on the general category, OBC, SC, and S.T. groups, and does not include information specifically on Muslims. As a result, it is impossible to ascertain the representation or percentage of Muslims in the non-teaching staff based on this survey.

Although the roots of marginalization and social exclusion have existed for a considerable period, what is particularly notable is the recent escalation of such marginalization and exclusion. This can be attributed to several factors, primarily within the context of the increasing influence of 'Hindu majoritarianism'. The rise of Hindu majoritarianism has contributed to a climate characterized by polarization and religious tensions, resulting in an environment where marginalized and excluded communities, including Muslims, face heightened discrimination and exclusion. Various factors, such as the influence of communal ideologies, likely play a significant role in explaining the acceleration of marginalization experienced by Muslims in recent times. For instance; the prospects for Muslims in terms of job opportunities appear increasingly bleak, as they face a higher rate of job scarcity compared to other social and religious groups. In fact, among different socio-religious communities, Muslims experience the highest unemployment rate. This disparity is evident in the data, which reveals a significant rise in the percentage of regular/ salaried Muslim workers who reported no work during the reference week, escalating from 1.6% in 2018-19 to 13.2% in 2019-20 (Oxfam India,2022).

These figures reflect a long-standing trend of discrimination in the job market that has been well-documented through surveys. Research consistently demonstrates that when identical resumes are submitted with Brahmin, Dalit, and Muslim names, applicants with Muslim names are at a distinct disadvantage, receiving the lowest percentage of interview invitations. This discriminatory practice underscores the systemic hurdles faced by Muslims when seeking employment, contributing to their disproportionately high unemployment rate and diminishing their prospects for a secure livelihood (Sukhadeo, Attewell, 2007).

From public spaces and a sense of insecurity. As a result, many Muslims may feel compelled to prioritize their safety and retreat into their communities. This withdrawal can manifest in the form of ghettoization, where Muslim populations concentrate in specific neighborhoods or areas

for a sense of In the challenging circumstances outlined above, many individuals from the Muslim community may find themselves lacking sufficient financial resources to pursue higher education. Instead, they may be compelled to work to support themselves and their families. Consequently, this economic necessity often leads to a higher dropout rate among Muslim youth, who are unable to continue their studies and are compelled to engage in manual labor or low-paying self-employment.

These circumstances highlight the socio-economic realities faced by many Muslims, where the need to earn a livelihood takes precedence over educational pursuits. Engagements in traditional trades such as weaving and car repair, commonly associated with the Muslim community, become avenues for employment due to their accessibility and familiarity. However, these occupations typically offer limited financial stability and career growth prospects (Singh, Gopal, 1982).

The combination of financial constraints, limited access to educational opportunities, and the necessity to earn a living contribute to the persistence of the high dropout rate among Muslim youth. This pattern further reinforces the existing socio-economic disparities and poses challenges to the community's overall progress and socio-economic mobility.

The violence and discrimination faced by Muslims can have profound psychological and socio-economic effects, leading to a withdrawal security and solidarity.

The process of ghettoization can have implications for educational opportunities and representation. The concentration of Muslim populations in specific areas may limit their access to quality education, resources, and opportunities in more diverse and inclusive educational environments. The limited spatial mobility resulting from violence and the segregation of communities can restrict the ability of Muslim students to access educational institutions outside their immediate neighborhoods.

In the current context, it becomes evident that the most rational and justifiable policy for the government would be to implement positive discrimination measures in favour of Muslims, as recommended by both the Sachar Committee Report and the Mishra Report, with the latter report placing even greater emphasis on this need. There are positive outcomes, as mentioned earlier, in Southern states that implement these policies, such as Kerala.

However, it is disheartening to note that The Ministry of Minority Affairs has discontinued the MANF fellowship, a dedicated initiative to support minority students pursuing higher education. The decision further restricts access to educational opportunities for minority students, including Muslims, and hampers their ability to pursue higher studies. Similarly, the decision of the BJP government in Karnataka to abolish the provision that had been providing Muslims with a sub-quota of 4 percent within the OBC quota. This decision not only diminishes the opportunities available to Muslim students but also undermines the progress made toward promoting inclusivity and bridging educational gaps.

These developments raise concern about the diminishing state support for Muslims, which goes against the recommendations of the Sachar Committee Report and the Mishra Report. These reports highlight the necessity of affirmative action to uplift marginalized communities and promote equal educational opportunities. The discontinuation of the Maulana Azad Fellowship and the scrapping of the sub-quota in Karnataka signify a regression in efforts to address educational disparities and promote the educational advancement of Muslim students.

To ensure a more equitable and inclusive society, it is imperative for the government to reconsider its policies and take proactive measures to reinstate or introduce support mechanisms for Muslim students. By implementing positive discrimination measures and providing targeted support, the government can contribute to bridging the educational divide and fostering a more inclusive educational system that empowers all marginalized communities, including Muslims, to thrive and succeed.

Conclusion

We have witnessed a persistent policy of discrimination aimed at undermining the access of vulnerable minorities to higher education. Such discriminatory practices are typically observed in countries with the explicit objective of creating a class of second-class citizens. While these measures may have achieved their intended purpose, they have never led to the harmonious development of societies.

By deliberately hindering the educational opportunities of marginalized communities, these discriminatory policies perpetuate inequality and hinder social progress. Denying individuals equal access to higher education based on their minority status not only infringes upon their

fundamental rights but also obstructs the overall development and cohesion of societies.

History has shown that societies built on principles of equality and inclusivity tend to thrive and achieve sustainable progress. In contrast, the deliberate marginalization of certain groups through discriminatory policies in the realm of education hampers the potential of individuals and undermines the overall well-being of communities.

Therefore, it is crucial for societies to recognize the detrimental effects of discriminatory practices targeting access to higher education and to actively inclusive policies that prioritize equal opportunities for all, irrespective of their minority status. By embracing diversity, fostering inclusivity, and dismantling discriminatory barriers, societies can work towards achieving harmonious development and realizing the full potential of their citizens.

References

- Dirghangi, A., Anas, O., & Team, C. (2023, February 27). *Education, Citizenship and Democracy - Centre for Studies of Plural Societies*. Centre for Studies of Plural Societies. <https://cspindia.org/education-citizenship-and-democracy>
- Easton, David. (1953). *The Political System: An Inquiry Into the State of Political Science*. New York: Knop.
- Hasan, Zoya, *Politics of Inclusion: Castes, Minorities, and Affirmative Action*, chapter (Muslim Backwardness and the Elusive Promise of Affirmative Action) p.160-191, 2011; online Oxford University Press.
- India Discrimination Report 2022. (2022). In <http://www.oxfamindia.org>. Oxfam. Retrieved September 15, 2023, from <https://www.oxfamindia.org/knowledgehub/workingpaper/india-discrimination-report-2022>
- Jaffrelot, Christophe, and Kalaiyarasan A. "Muslims in Higher Education: A Sobering Tale." *The Indian Express*, May 9, 2023. <https://indianexpress.com/article/opinion/columns/lower-in-higher-education-8598739/>. Accessed 21/6/2023.
- Kabeer N. (2006). Social exclusion and the MDGs: The challenge of 'durable inequalities' in the Asian context. *Asia 2015 Conference*, 6–7 March 2006.
- Kundu, Amitabh, *Post Sachar Evaluation Report (2014)*, Government of India, New Delhi.

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Mishra, Ranganath,(2007). The National Commission for Religious and Linguistic Minorities, Government of India, New Delhi.

Murthy, K, Sanjay,().All India Survey on Higher Education 2020-21, Ministry of Education, Department of Higher Education, Government of India, New Delhi.

Sen, A. (1999). Development as Freedom (*Women's Agency and Social Change*) p.184-193,1st ed.New York, Knopf.

Singh, G. (1983). Gopal Singh Committee, Government of India, New Delhi

Sukhadeo, & Attewell. (2007, October 13). The Legacy of Social Exclusion. *Economic and Political Weekly, Vol. 42*(41).

T.K. (2022, February 23). The hijab ban threatens Muslim women's access to Education. <http://thefrontline.thehindu.com>. Retrieved July 10, 2023.

The Indian Express. "Over 1,000 Muslim Girls Dropped out of P.U. Colleges in Karnataka during Hijab Controversy: PUCL Report," January 10, 2023. <https://indianexpress.com/article/cities/bangalore/pucl-releases-report-on-impact-of-hijab-ban-on-muslim-girl-stu>.

The wire Staff. (2022, December 9). *Union Government Discontinues MANF Scholarship for Minority Communities*. <http://thewire.in>. Retrieved July 10, 2023, from <https://thewire.in/education/manf-minority-smriti-irani-sachar-committee>

Note

* For Muslims, this data for the B.sc course was received from 9 universities belonging to 6 states, out of a total of 2698 students who appeared in this examination, the number of Muslim students was 92, whereas for Sikhs, information was received from 4 universities belonging to 3 states, out of a total of 4947 students who appeared in this examination. The number of students was 84, on the other hand, for Christians this information was received from 5 universities belonging to 3 states, out of a total of 5073 students the number of appeared students was 367.

For Muslims. This data for the MBBS course was received from 12 universities belonging to 8 states, out of a total of 2845 students number of appeared Muslims were 98. In contrast, for Sikhas, information was received from 4 universities belonging to 4 states, out of a total of 1456 students appeared in this examination the number of Sikh students was 108, on the other hand, for Christians this data was received from 6 universities of 5 states, out of a total of 2816 students, Who appeared in this examination, the number of Christian students was 173.